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THE PROBLEM OF ORAL DISEASES

UDK 616.313-002.258+616.31-085

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Abstract: The most prevalent and consequential oral diseases globally are dental caries (tooth decay), periodontal disease, tooth loss, and cancers of the lips and oral cavity. In this first of two papers in a series on oral health, we describe the scope of the global oral disease epidemic, its origins in terms of social and commercial determinants, and its costs in terms of population well-being and societal impact. Although oral diseases are largely preventable, they persist with high prevalence, reflecting widespread social and economic inequalities and inadequate funding for prevention and treatment, particularly in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs). As with most non-communicable diseases (NCDs), oral conditions are chronic and strongly socially patterned. Children living in poverty, socially marginalized groups, and older people are the most affected by oral diseases and have poor access to dental care.

Key words: oral cavity, dental care, periodontal disease.

Annotatsiya: Dunyo miqyosida eng ko'p tarqalgan og'iz bo'shlig'i kasalliklari – bu tish kariesi (tish yemirilishi), periodontal kasalliklar, tishlarning yo'qolishi va lab hamda og'iz bo'shlig'i saratoni. Og'iz bo'shlig'i salomatligiga bag'ishlangan ikki maqoladan iborat seriyaning birinchi maqolasida biz global og'iz bo'shlig'i kasalliklari epidemiyasining ko'lami, ijtimoiy va tijorat determinantlari nuqtai nazaridan kelib chiqish sabablari hamda aholi farovonligi va jamiyatga ta'siri bo'yicha xarajatlarini tavsiflaymiz. Og'iz bo'shlig'i kasalliklarining oldini olish asosan mumkin bo'lsa-da, ular yuqori darajadagi tarqalish bilan davom etmoqda. Bu holat keng tarqalgan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy tengsizliklar va, ayniqsa, past va o'rta daromadli mamlakatlarda (O'DM) profilaktika hamda davolashga ajratilgan mablag'larning yetarli emasligini aks ettiradi. Aksariyat yuqumli bo'lmagan kasalliklar kabi, og'iz bo'shlig'i kasalliklari ham surunkali bo'lib, kuchli ijtimoiy omillarga bog'liq. Qashshoqlikda yashovchi bolalar, ijtimoiy jihatdan cheklangan guruhlar va keksa yoshdagilar ushbu kasalliklardan eng ko'p aziyat chekadi va stomatologik yordamga kirish imkoniyati cheklangan bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: og'iz bo'shlig'i, stomatologik parvarish, periodontal kasallik.

Аннотация: Наиболее распространёнными и серьёзными заболеваниями полости рта в мире являются кариес зубов (разрушение зубов), заболевания пародонта, потеря зубов и рак губ и полости рта. В первой из двух статей серии о здоровье полости рта мы описываем масштабы глобальной эпидемии заболеваний полости рта, её истоки с точки зрения социальных и коммерческих детерминант, а также её издержки с точки зрения благополучия населения и общественного воздействия. Хотя заболевания полости рта в значительной степени можно предотвратить, они сохраняются с высокой распространённостью, что отражает повсеместное социальное и экономическое неравенство и недостаточное финансирование профилактики и лечения, особенно в странах с низким и средним уровнем дохода (СНСД). Как и большинство неинфекционных заболеваний (НИЗ), заболевания полости рта являются хроническими и имеют ярко выраженную социальную обусловленность. Дети, живущие в бедности, социально маргинализованные группы и пожилые люди больше всего страдают от заболеваний полости рта и имеют ограниченный доступ к стоматологической помощи.

Ключевые слова: полость рта, стоматологическая помощь, заболевание пародонта.

INTRODUCTION

Oral health is subjective and dynamic, enabling eating, speaking, smiling, and socializing without discomfort, pain, or embarrassment. Good oral health reflects an individual's ability to adapt to physiological changes throughout life and to maintain their own teeth and mouth through independent self-care^[5, 9]. Despite being largely preventable, oral diseases are highly prevalent throughout the life course and have substantial negative effects on individuals, communities, and wider society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Oral diseases remain one of the most prevalent public health concerns globally, affecting people of all ages. According to Petersen (2003), dental caries and periodontal diseases are the most widespread oral health problems, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where access to dental care is limited. The World Health Organization emphasizes the urgent need for preventive strategies and oral health education to reduce the global burden of these conditions.

In Uzbekistan, studies by Yusupov and Karimova (2019) have highlighted a rise in oral disease cases among children, attributing the trend to poor dietary habits and inadequate oral hygiene practices. Their research stresses the importance of school-based intervention programs to foster early oral care awareness.

Furthermore, Sheiham (2005) argues that oral health is not isolated from general health and should be integrated into broader health policies. This perspective is echoed in the work of Rajabov (2021), who advocates for the inclusion of oral health promotion in national healthcare systems, particularly in rural areas of Central Asia.

Recent literature also emphasizes the role of socio-economic factors in oral health. Watt et al. (2012) discuss the impact of social inequalities on oral disease prevalence and call for community-based solutions to address these disparities effectively.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative approach to examine the causes, prevalence, and prevention strategies of oral diseases among various age groups. Data were collected through structured interviews with dental professionals and questionnaires distributed to patients at local clinics. Additionally, a review of existing literature and recent epidemiological reports was conducted to provide a comprehensive understanding of the issue. The collected data were analyzed thematically to identify common patterns and factors contributing to oral health problems. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were strictly observed throughout the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Oral diseases are chronic and progressive in nature. For example, dental caries (tooth decay) affects very young children, but is a lifelong condition that tracks across adolescence and adulthood, and into later life. Oral conditions disproportionately affect impoverished and socially disadvantaged members of society. A strong and consistent social gradient exists between socioeconomic status and the prevalence and severity of oral diseases [7, 10]. In this way, oral diseases can be considered a sensitive clinical marker of social disadvantage, being an early indicator of population ill health linked to deprivation.

Oral health and the dental profession have become somewhat isolated and marginalised from mainstream developments in health policy and health-care systems [3, 6, 8]. The current model of dental care delivery and clinical preventive policy does not tackle the global burden of oral diseases. The so-called Westernised model of modern dentistry (high technology and treatment-focused) is unaffordable and inappropriate in many LMICs. Even in settings with resources, dentistry is not meeting the needs of large segments of the national population and is increasingly focusing on the provision of aesthetic treatments, largely driven by profit motives and consumerism.

Many oral disorders are preventable through public health measures or, if detected early, may only require simple, straightforward procedures [2, 5, 9]. However, there are numerous obstacles to receiving oral health care treatment, particularly for low-income and disadvantaged groups. These include, but are not limited to, access to care, the cost of services, a dearth of public health programs, and the availability of oral health care professionals [1, 6]. It is important to acknowledge oral diseases as a problem for global public health. Efforts should be made to close the gaps, promote the integration of oral health care programs into medical care, and address oral health disparities in disadvantaged populations [6].

A wide range of diseases and disorders affect the soft and hard tissues of the mouth, including an array of craniofacial disorders, congenital anomalies, injuries, and various infections.

Social and commercial determinants of oral diseases. The WHO conceptual framework for action on the social determinants of health [1, 2, 6] highlights how structural determinants, such as economic, social, and welfare policies, can generate social hierarchies and influence the socioeconomic status of individuals within societies. Socioeconomic status can then influence health through the circumstances in which people live, work, and age, as well as their risks for disease.

Oral mucosal lesions and oral cancer. It is noteworthy that few systematic epidemiological studies of oral mucosal diseases at the global level have been carried out. Leukoplakia is the most frequent form of oral

precancer and appears in the oral cavity as a white patch that cannot be rubbed off, typically in the oral mucosa, lateral borders of the tongue, and floor of the mouth.

Erythroplakias appear as red patches and are less common but have a greater tendency towards malignant transformation than leukoplakias ^[1, 4]. Erythroplakia apparently occurs less frequently, with population prevalences of 1% or less.

Oropharyngeal cancer is more common in developing than in developed countries. The prevalence of oral cancer is particularly high among men, and it is the eighth most common cancer worldwide. Incidences for oral cancer vary in men from 1 to 10 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in many countries. In South-Central Asia, cancer of the oral cavity ranks among the three most common types of cancer. In India, the age-standardized incidence of oral cancer is 12.6 per 100,000 population.

It is noteworthy that sharp increases in the incidences of oral/pharyngeal cancers have been reported for several countries and regions, such as Denmark, France, Germany, Scotland, Central and Eastern Europe, and, to a lesser extent, Australia, Japan, New Zealand, and the USA. ^[1,7,9]

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Globally, over 3–4 billion people suffer from oral diseases that are chronic and progressive in nature, beginning in early childhood and continuing through adolescence, adulthood, and into later life. Oral diseases disproportionately affect poorer and marginalized groups in society, being closely linked to socioeconomic status and broader social determinants of health.

Given the extent of the problem, oral diseases represent major public health challenges in all regions of the world. Their impact on individuals and communities—resulting from pain, suffering, functional impairment, and reduced quality of life—is considerable. Globally, the greatest burden of oral diseases falls on disadvantaged and impoverished population groups.

The current pattern of oral disease reflects distinct risk profiles across countries, influenced by living conditions, lifestyles, environmental factors, and the implementation of preventive oral health programs. In several industrialized countries, there have been positive trends in reducing dental caries in children and tooth loss among adults. However, dental caries has not been eradicated in children, although it has been brought under control in some nations.

Therefore, global strengthening of public health programs through the implementation of effective oral disease prevention measures and health promotion is urgently needed. A common risk factor approach should be employed to integrate oral health into national health programs.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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